

Bacterial Causes of Tonsillitis among Adults and Their Relationship with Oxidative Stress Markers

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Abstract

Background: Tonsillitis in adults is often caused by *Streptococcus pyogenes*, and is accompanied by oxidative stress, which affects inflammation and the development of the disease. **Aims of the study:** This research proposes to determine the bacteria responsible for adult tonsillitis and to assess their association with oxidative stress markers to understand their impact on disease pathogenicity and disease course. **Methodology:** In this case-control study, 150 patients (100 cases and 50 controls) were enrolled at University of Babylon faculty of dentistry between August 10, 2025 and April 20, 2026. Participants were diagnosed with symptoms and throat culture. Participants were adults (≥ 18 years) without chronic illness, prior antibiotic use, or pregnancy. Blood (5 ml) was taken, centrifuged and frozen at -20°C . Oxidative stress markers were measured by ELISA (BioTechne, USA). Data were analyzed via SPSS version 26, $p < 0.05$ was used as cut off value. **Result:** Age ($p = 0.38$), sex ($p = 0.82$) and smoking ($p = 0.36$) were not significantly different, but recurrent tonsillitis was significantly increased in patients ($p = 0.001$). Significant symptoms were found ($p < 0.001$). The most prevalent bacteria was *Streptococcus pyogenes*. Oxidative stress parameters were elevated MDA and low antioxidants ($p < 0.001$). There were significant differences among bacteria ($p = 0.041-0.048$) and varying antibiotic sensitivities. MDA was positively correlated and antioxidants negatively ($p < 0.001$). **Conclusions:** Oxidative stress, with elevated MDA and decreased antioxidant status is seen in bacterial tonsillitis, probably caused by excessive production of reactive oxygen species in response to infection. Streptococci induce more inflammation, leading to more oxidative stress and severity of disease.

Keywords: Tonsillitis, Bacterial infection, Oxidative stress, Antioxidant enzymes, *Streptococcus pyogenes*.

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Introduction

Tonsillitis is a frequently occurring inflammatory disease of the palatine tonsils that occurs in both children and adults, though it is under-recognised in the latter. It presents with a sore throat, fever, difficulty in swallowing, and swollen tonsils, often with exudate and cervical lymphadenopathy (Singh et al., 2023; Windfuhr et al., 2016). It may be caused by a variety of pathogens; but bacterial infections are still a significant cause, especially in moderate to severe disease. *Streptococcus pyogenes* is thought to be the most common bacterial pathogen, followed by *Streptococcus pneumoniae* and *Haemophilus influenzae*. These bacteria express virulence factors that promote colonization and tissue invasion, evasion of host immunity and induction of an inflammatory response (Bezega et al., 2023).

Pathophysiology of bacterial tonsillitis involves pathogen-host interactions. Bacterial infection stimulates innate immune cells (e.g., neutrophils, macrophages) and pro-inflammatory mediators such as cytokines and reactive oxygen species (ROS). While ROS are essential for bacterial killing, excessive production can induce oxidative stress and an imbalance in the production of pro-oxidants and antioxidant defences. This can lead to lipid, protein and DNA oxidation, and contribute to disease (Håkansson et al., 2018; Ankathil et al., 2025).

The contribution of oxidative stress in the onset of infectious and inflammatory disease is now recognised. For example, in tonsillitis, oxidative stress markers, such as malondialdehyde (MDA), have been shown to be elevated, suggesting that there is an increase in lipid peroxidation in the disease (Ozbay et al., 2016). Simultaneously, there has been decreased antioxidant enzyme activity, such as superoxide dismutase (SOD), glutathione peroxidase (GPx) and catalase, reflecting a loss of the body's protective reserve. These changes indicate that oxidative stress not only occurs in response to bacterial infection, but may also amplify the inflammatory response in tonsillar tissue (Meng et al., 2025).

While the involvement of oxidative stress in numerous infectious diseases is well documented, its association with bacterial tonsillitis, especially in adults, is not well studied (Sarkar & Sil, 2019). To date, such research has generally centred around children or has focused on bacterial identification but not biochemical indicators of oxidative stress. Also, differences in the bacterial profile of different geographical areas, due to environmental factors, antibiotic use and population factors, suggest the need for more regional studies (Shukla et al., 2020; Asher & Guilford, 2016).

Another crucial component is the growing problem of antibiotic-resistant strains of bacteria that cause tonsillitis. The indiscriminate use of antibiotics has led to antibiotic-resistant strains, making tonsillitis more difficult to treat, and more likely to recur (Katkowska et al., 2020). Therefore, information on the frequency of bacterial species and their resistance to antibiotics is essential for therapy. Moreover, integration of these bacterial findings with oxidative stress indicators could provide insight into the severity, progression of the disease and potentially new diagnostic/prognostic markers (Al-Tameemi et al., 2020; Jyothsna et al., 2021).

Using microbiological and biochemical data is an integrated approach to understanding tonsillitis. The investigation of both the bacterial pathogens and the oxidative stress response, leads to the understanding of tissue damage and disease. This may also help in the identification of therapeutic targets, such as antioxidants, to reduce the effect of oxidative damage and improve recovery (Samara et al., 2023; Kostić et al., 2022).

Therefore, the aim of this study is to investigate the aetiology of bacterial pathogens that cause tonsillitis in adults and to evaluate their relationship with markers of oxidative stress. By analysing the occurrence of bacterial pathogens in relation to markers of oxidative stress, this study aims to provide insight into the interplay between infection and response. This may in turn lead to the development of improved methods of diagnosing and treating adult tonsillitis.

Methodology

A case-control study was performed at the University of Babylon faculty of dentistry between August 10, 2025 and April 20, 2026, involving 150 subjects of which 100 adults with bacterial tonsillitis and 50 apparently healthy controls. Approval was obtained in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and written informed consent was obtained from all participants. Bacterial tonsillitis was diagnosed on the basis of clinical signs and symptoms, including sore throat, fever, dysphagia, tonsillar enlargement, and tonsillar exudate, in conjunction with microbiological evidence obtained by throat swab cultures under sterile conditions on blood agar and chocolate agar media, followed by identification using Gram staining and biochemical tests. The inclusion criteria were adult patients (age ≥ 18 years) with established bacterial

tonsillitis, not taking antioxidant supplements, and willing to participate; exclusion criteria were patients with viral infections, systemic diseases (including diabetes, autoimmune diseases, liver and kidney disease), those who had used antibiotics in the past 7-10 days before sampling, heavy smokers, and women who were pregnant or lactating. To perform laboratory tests, blood samples (5 mL) were obtained from each participant using sterile disposable syringes and were placed in EDTA tubes (2 mL) for complete blood count and ordinary gel tubes (3 mL) for the separation of serum, which was allowed to clot at room temperature and then centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 10 minutes to obtain the serum, which was stored at -20°C until further analysis. Biomarkers of oxidative stress were determined using commercially available enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) kits (BioTechne, USA), including malondialdehyde (MDA) as a measure of lipid peroxidation, and antioxidant enzymes such as superoxide dismutase (SOD), glutathione peroxidase (GPx), and catalase, as well as total antioxidant capacity (TAC) which was determined by colorimetric methods following the manufacturer's protocol. The assays were conducted under optimal laboratory conditions with proper quality control procedures and absorbance was measured using a microplate reader.

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS software version 26 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA), continuous variables presented as mean \pm standard deviation and categorical variables as frequencies and percentages; the independent t-test and Chi-square test were used to compare groups and the Spearman correlation coefficient was used to assess correlations, with a p-value of less than 0.05 considered statistically significant.

Ethical Approval

The study was approved by the human ethics committee of University of Babylon faculty of dentistry, Everyone who took part in the study was told about it and asked to sign a consent form. The patient was also guaranteed that his information would be kept private.

Results

Sociodemographic and Clinical Characteristics of Adult Patients with Tonsillitis and Healthy Controls

The comparative study showed no significant differences between the patients and the controls in terms of age ($p = 0.38$) and sex, in males ($p = 0.82$) and females ($p = 0.82$), implying that the baseline characteristics of the two groups were comparable. Likewise, there was no significant difference in smoking status ($p = 0.36$). However, a significant association was found in recurrent tonsillitis history, which was more common in patients than controls ($p = 0.001$). Similarly, clinical symptoms exhibited high significance with fever ($p < 0.001$), sore throat ($p < 0.001$), dysphagia ($p < 0.001$) and tonsillar exudate ($p < 0.001$) showing higher prevalence in tonsillitis patients, as these symptoms are highly correlated with the presence of active bacterial tonsillitis (Table 1).

Table 1. Comparative Analysis of Demographic Variables and Clinical Presentations Between Study Groups

Variable	Tonsillitis patients n=100	Controls n=50	p-value
Age, years	31.6 \pm 9.4	30.2 \pm 8.7	0.38
Male	54 (54.0%)	26 (52.0%)	0.82
Female	46 (46.0%)	24 (48.0%)	0.82
Smoking	29 (29.0%)	11 (22.0%)	0.36
Recurrent tonsillitis history	38 (38.0%)	6 (12.0%)	0.001

Fever	67 (67.0%)	3 (6.0%)	<0.001
Sore throat	94 (94.0%)	4 (8.0%)	<0.001
Dysphagia	61 (61.0%)	2 (4.0%)	<0.001
Tonsillar exudate	49 (49.0%)	0 (0.0%)	<0.001

Distribution of Bacterial Isolates Among Adult Patients with Tonsillitis

Microbiological study in the table 2, showed that *Streptococcus pyogenes* was the most common pathogen (31.0%), followed by *Streptococcus pneumoniae* (18.0%) and *Haemophilus influenzae* (14.0%). Gram-negative organisms, such as *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (10.0%), *Escherichia coli* (7.0%) and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (5.0%) were also present, with *Moraxella catarrhalis* accounting for 4.0% of isolates. Interestingly, 11.0% of samples did not produce growth of any kind, which could be due to subclinical antibiotic ingestion or non-culturable or viral causes. The data reflect the dominance of streptococcal species as the most common bacterial pathogens causing tonsillitis in adults, and the minor but significant role of Gram-negative bacteria.

Table 2. Distribution of Bacterial Isolates Among Adult Patients with Tonsillitis

Bacterial isolate	Number	Percentage
<i>Streptococcus pyogenes</i>	31	31.0%
<i>Streptococcus pneumoniae</i>	18	18.0%
<i>Haemophilus influenzae</i>	14	14.0%
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	10	10.0%
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	7	7.0%
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	5	5.0%
<i>Moraxella catarrhalis</i>	4	4.0%
No bacterial growth	11	11.0%
Total	100	100%

Comparison of Oxidative Stress and Antioxidant Markers Between Tonsillitis Patients and Healthy Controls

The result of oxidative stress in the table 3, demonstrated a significant elevation in lipid peroxidation in patients with tonsillitis, as measured by levels of MDA ($p < 0.001$). Conversely, antioxidant defense systems were significantly down-regulated in patients, such as SOD ($p < 0.001$), GPx ($p < 0.001$) and catalase ($p < 0.001$). Similarly, total antioxidant capacity was significantly decreased in patients, compared to controls ($p < 0.001$). Thus, the results demonstrate a marked shift in the pro-oxidant-antioxidant balance in tonsillitis patients, reflecting the presence of significant oxidative stress during tonsillitis.

Table 3. Assessment of Lipid Peroxidation and Antioxidant Defense Status in Study Groups

Marker	Tonsillitis patients n=100	Controls n=50	p-value
MDA, nmol/mL	5.42 ± 1.31	3.18 ± 0.86	<0.001
SOD, U/mL	38.7 ± 9.6	51.4 ± 10.8	<0.001
GPx, U/L	41.2 ± 8.9	49.6 ± 9.7	<0.001
Catalase, U/mL	22.8 ± 6.4	29.3 ± 7.1	<0.001
Total antioxidant capacity, mmol/L	1.18 ± 0.31	1.52 ± 0.35	<0.001

Variation of Oxidative Stress Markers According to Bacterial Isolates in Adult Tonsillitis Patients

Comparing the oxidative stress markers among different bacterial pathogens showed statistically significant differences in MDA ($p = 0.041$), SOD ($p = 0.048$) and total antioxidant capacity ($p = 0.039$);

however, GPx levels did not differ significantly ($p = 0.216$). In particular, *Streptococcus pyogenes* had the highest MDA levels and lowest antioxidant enzyme activities, suggesting a higher degree of oxidative stress compared with other bacteria. Likewise, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* displayed relatively high levels of oxidative stress. On the other hand, *Moraxella catarrhalis* and *Escherichia coli* infections showed relatively lower MDA levels and increased antioxidant enzyme activities. These results indicate that the extent of oxidative stress is dependent on the bacterial pathogen, with more pathogenic bacteria showing greater oxidative stress as shown in the table 4.

Table 4. Comparative Analysis of Oxidative and Antioxidant Parameters across Different Bacterial Pathogens

Bacterial isolate	MDA nmol/mL	SOD U/mL	GPx U/L	TAC mmol/L
<i>Streptococcus pyogenes</i>	5.86 ± 1.22	35.9 ± 8.4	39.1 ± 8.1	1.09 ± 0.27
<i>Streptococcus pneumoniae</i>	5.48 ± 1.18	37.6 ± 8.9	40.8 ± 8.5	1.15 ± 0.29
<i>Haemophilus influenzae</i>	5.21 ± 1.09	39.2 ± 9.1	41.6 ± 8.7	1.20 ± 0.30
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	5.33 ± 1.26	38.1 ± 9.3	40.2 ± 8.4	1.17 ± 0.31
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	5.01 ± 1.14	40.4 ± 9.0	42.7 ± 8.6	1.24 ± 0.32
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	5.74 ± 1.31	36.8 ± 8.6	39.6 ± 8.2	1.11 ± 0.28
<i>Moraxella catarrhalis</i>	4.91 ± 1.08	41.3 ± 9.4	43.1 ± 8.8	1.27 ± 0.33
p-value	0.041	0.048	0.216	0.039

Antibiotic Susceptibility Patterns of Bacterial Isolates in Adult Tonsillitis Patients

The antibiotic susceptibility testing in the table 5, revealed wide variations in the responses of the different antibiotics, with ceftriaxone (76.4%) and levofloxacin (73.0%) being most sensitive, followed by amoxicillin–clavulanic acid (70.8%) and cefotaxime (68.5%). Intermediate sensitivity levels were found for ciprofloxacin (64.0%), gentamicin (60.7%) and azithromycin (58.4%), with the lowest sensitivity for trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole (43.8%). Relative resistance was higher for trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole (42.7%), azithromycin (25.9%), ciprofloxacin (24.7%) and gentamicin (24.7%) whilst lower for ceftriaxone (13.5%) and amoxicillin-clavulanic acid (15.7%). The intermediate response rates varied from 9.0% to 15.7% for all the antibiotics. In general, these results demonstrate a statistically significant difference in the efficacy of antibiotics, which is reflective of the growing pattern of resistance and the need for specific antibiotic therapy guided by antibiotic susceptibility tests.

Table 5. Distribution of Sensitivity, Intermediate Response, and Resistance among Commonly Used Antibiotics

Antibiotic	Sensitive n (%)	Intermediate n (%)	Resistant n (%)
Amoxicillin–clavulanic acid	63 (70.8%)	12 (13.5%)	14 (15.7%)
Ceftriaxone	68 (76.4%)	9 (10.1%)	12 (13.5%)
Cefotaxime	61 (68.5%)	11 (12.4%)	17 (19.1%)
Azithromycin	52 (58.4%)	14 (15.7%)	23 (25.9%)
Ciprofloxacin	57 (64.0%)	10 (11.2%)	22 (24.7%)
Levofloxacin	65 (73.0%)	8 (9.0%)	16 (18.0%)
Gentamicin	54 (60.7%)	13 (14.6%)	22 (24.7%)
Trimethoprim–sulfamethoxazole	39 (43.8%)	12 (13.5%)	38 (42.7%)

Correlation Between Oxidative Stress Markers and Clinical Severity in Adult Tonsillitis

The correlation study showed a strong positive correlation between MDA levels and severity ($r = 0.46$, $p < 0.001$), suggesting that as the severity of tonsillitis increases, so does lipid peroxidation. In contrast,

antioxidant markers showed significant negative correlations with clinical severity, including SOD ($r = -0.39$, $p < 0.001$), GPx ($r = -0.31$, $p = 0.002$), catalase ($r = -0.28$, $p = 0.005$), and total antioxidant capacity ($r = -0.35$, $p < 0.001$). This implies that as tonsillitis progresses, the antioxidant status is impaired, and the oxidative stress increases, indicating a marked imbalance between pro-oxidant and antioxidant processes as shown in the table 6.

Table 6. Spearman Correlation Analysis of Pro-oxidant and Antioxidant Parameters with Disease Severity

Marker	r-value	p-value
MDA	0.46	<0.001
SOD	-0.39	<0.001
GPx	-0.31	0.002
Catalase	-0.28	0.005
Total antioxidant capacity	-0.35	<0.001

Discussion

Our research is a comprehensive evaluation of the bacterial agents responsible for adult tonsillitis and the association with oxidative stress. Our results demonstrate an association between infection and oxidative stress, which reflects the inflammatory response and immune response to the infection by the pathogenic bacteria.

The sociodemographic analysis did not reveal any significant differences between patients and controls (age and sex) suggesting they are demographically similar. However, the increased number of clinical symptoms (fever, dysphagia and tonsillar exudate) among the patients is in line with the inflammatory response described in tonsillitis. This supports previous reports that have highlighted the clinical symptoms of bacterial tonsillitis, particularly recurrent tonsillitis in adults (Guntinas-Lichius et al., 2023). The higher prevalence in recurrent tonsillitis also suggests the possibility of recurrent or persistent microbial colonisation and immune dysfunction, as has been reported (Johnston et al., 2018).

The bacterial distribution in this study, where *Streptococcus pyogenes* was the most common isolate, followed by *Streptococcus pneumoniae* and *Haemophilus influenzae*, is in line with the pathogenic bacteria that are known to cause upper respiratory infections (Lobb et al., 2023). These bacteria are reported to have virulence factors (adhesins and exotoxins) that facilitate infection and invasion. This is also in line with the previous studies both in local and international settings (Sarkar et al., 2021). However, the presence of Gram-negative bacteria, such as *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Escherichia coli* in some patients may indicate possible contamination, poor hygiene, or secondary infection. However, other studies reported that *Staphylococcus aureus* was more prevalent in patients with tonsillitis (Cerceo et al., 2016), which was excluded from our study. This variation could be due to differences in sampling methods, culture media, or inclusion and exclusion criteria. For instance, contamination of the swab or inclusion of commensal organisms in those studies might result in an overestimation of *Staphylococcus aureus* (Leal et al., 2019).

The results of the oxidative stress analysis showed a marked elevation in MDA levels and a reduction in antioxidant parameters (SOD, GPx, catalase and total antioxidant capacity) in the patients group compared with the control group. This suggests increased lipid peroxidation and antioxidant depletion in response to an increased generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS). Our results are consistent with other studies showing increased oxidative stress in infectious and inflammatory diseases, such as tonsillitis and other respiratory infections (Sarkar & Sil, 2019; Ozbay et al., 2016). The elevated levels of MDA are specifically linked to damage of membrane lipids, and the decreased antioxidant enzymes reflect dysfunction of the antioxidant defences (Yekti et al., 2018).

As shown in the distribution of oxidative stress markers across bacterial species, the maximum level of oxidative stress was associated with *Streptococcus pyogenes* infections. The virulence of this pathogen may have triggered a strong neutrophilic response and increased formation of ROS via respiratory burst (Nicchi, 2022). This is consistent with other studies of streptococcal infections and oxidative stress (Hernández-Morfa et al., 2023; Sánchez-Villamil et al., 2020). On the other hand, infections with lower virulence bacteria, such as *Moraxella catarrhalis*, exhibited lower oxidative stress, indicating that the oxidative stress response is dependent on the extent of bacterial virulence and host immune response (Nicchi, 2022).

But these results are not entirely supported by other studies. Other studies have found no changes in antioxidant enzymes in mild or early-stage infections (Yao et al., 2022). This variation could be due to several factors, such as the severity of infection, stage of infection and nutritional status of the patients. For example, antioxidant enzymes are highly dependent on dietary vitamin and trace metal consumption, such as zinc and selenium. Other factors include differences in laboratory techniques, such as sensitivity of the assay, and sample preparation (Rani et al., 2022).

The results of the antibiotic susceptibility tests in this study show high susceptibility to β -lactam antibiotics and fluoroquinolones, and moderate resistance to macrolides and trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole. This is in line with international trends of increasing antibiotic resistance, resulting from widespread and often inappropriate use of antibiotics (Zeynudin et al., 2018). Elevated resistance to some antibiotics could be due to local antibiotic prescribing patterns and the presence of over-the-counter antibiotics. However, other studies have shown higher susceptibility to macrolides (Su et al., 2023), which could be related to better antibiotic stewardship policies. Consequently, the regional differences in resistance patterns continue to have a significant impact on treatment.

Moderate positive correlation between MDA and disease severity, and negative correlations with antioxidant factors were found in the correlation analysis. This implies that oxidative stress not only occurs during infection but also plays a role in disease progression. This is due to damage caused by ROS, stimulation of pro-inflammatory cytokines, and a further escalation of the inflammatory response. Our results are consistent with research reporting a link between oxidative stress and severity of infectious diseases (Ozbay et al., 2016). But the moderate correlations suggest that oxidative stress is one of many factors contributing to the severity of disease (Zorlu et al., 2022).

Limitations

There are several important aspects that contribute to variability. First, study design (cross-sectional versus longitudinal) could affect analysis of causality. Second, differences in demographic factors, such as age, gender, health status and immune status, could influence bacterial diversity and antioxidant responses. Third, exposure to the environment (for example pollution and socioeconomic status) may affect bacterial exposure and antioxidant status. Finally, there is variability in the bacterial identification and biochemical methods used.

Conclusion

Lastly, our study confirms that bacterial tonsillitis is associated with a high level of oxidative stress and that this varies with the pathogen. Our findings are in general agreement with the existing literature, but differences suggest caution in the interpretation of studies, allowing for the possible differences in methodology and populations. We believe future studies should include larger sample sizes and longitudinal follow-up to aid in understanding the mechanisms by which bacterial infections, oxidative stress and health are related.

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